

High reflectance Cr/V multilayer with B₄C barrier layer for water window wavelength region

Qiushi Huang¹, Jiani Fei¹, Yang Liu¹, Pin Li¹, Mingwu Wen¹, Chun Xie², Philippe Jonnard^{3,4}, Angelo Giglia⁵, Zhong Zhang¹, Kun Wang⁶, Zhanshan Wang^{1*}

¹ Key Laboratory of Advanced Micro-Structured Materials MOE, Institute of Precision Optical Engineering, School of Physics Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

² Sino-German College of Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

³ Sorbonne Universités, UPMC Univ Paris 06, Laboratoire de Chimie Physique - Matière et Rayonnement, 11 rue Pierre et Marie Curie, F-75231 Paris cedex 05, France

⁴ CNRS UMR 7614, Laboratoire de Chimie Physique - Matière et Rayonnement, 11 rue Pierre et Marie Curie, F-75231 Paris cedex 05, France

⁵ CNR Istituto Officina Materiali 34149 Trieste, Italy

⁶ College of Mechanical Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

*Corresponding author: wanzqs@tongji.edu.cn

Received XX Month XXXX; revised XX Month, XXXX; accepted XX Month XXXX; posted XX Month XXXX (Doc. ID XXXXX); published XX Month XXXX

To develop high reflectance mirror for the short wavelength range of the water window region ($\lambda=2.42$ nm-2.73 nm), Cr/V multilayers with B₄C barrier layers are studied. The grazing incidence X-ray reflectometry results show that the multilayer interface widths are significantly reduced down to 0.21-0.31 nm, after the introduction of 0.1 nm B₄C barrier layers at both interfaces. The [B₄C/Cr/B₄C/V] multilayer with a large number of bilayers of N=300 maintains the same small interface width while the surface roughness is only 0.2 nm. According to the transmission electron microscope measurements, the layer structure improvement with barrier layers can be attributed to the suppression of the crystallization of vanadium inside the structure. Based on the interface engineered multilayer, a maximum soft X-ray reflectance of 24.3% is achieved at $\lambda=2.441$ nm, under the grazing incidence of 42°.

OCIS codes: (340.7480) X-rays, soft x-rays, extreme ultraviolet (EUV); (340.7470) X-ray mirrors; (310.1860) Deposition and fabrication;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/OL.99.099999>

Soft X-ray (SXR) microscopy has experienced significant development during the last decade, particularly driven by the application of biological imaging in the water window region ($\lambda=2.3$ -4.4 nm) [1,2]. Spatial resolution of 10 nm has been realized with synchrotron radiation sources and state-of-the-art X-ray optics [3], while the resolution limit can be further pushed downward by lensless methods of coherent diffraction imaging [4]. Compact soft X-ray

microscopes have also been widely used in lab with spatial resolution below 50 nm [5].

Multilayer mirror is an important component for the water window SXR microscope. They are typically used as the collector, imaging optics, or polarizer which all require high reflectance in the first place [6,7]. Given to the short wavelengths of the water window region, each layer thickness of the multilayer is extremely small, below 1 nm, which makes the fabrication of high reflectance multilayer very challenging [7]. Sc-, Ti-, and V-based multilayers are selected in this range based on their absorption edges at $\lambda=3.12$ nm, 2.73 nm, and 2.42 nm, respectively. Among these, Cr/Sc multilayer is most widely studied working above the Sc L-edge [8,9,10]. By using B₄C barrier layer or incorporation of nitrogen, the layer structure can be significantly improved and a maximum reflectance of 32% was obtained at 3.11 nm at near normal incidence [11]. Cr/V multilayer is the most promising multilayer candidate working from 2.42 nm to 2.73 nm with high theoretical reflectance. Nevertheless, this multilayer is much less studied compared to Cr/Sc. A maximal normal incidence reflectance of 9% for Cr/V with barrier layers was reported by Gullikson et al, while the fabricated multilayer structure and the physical mechanism were absent [11]. In this paper, we will present our work on the interface engineered Cr/V multilayer with B₄C barrier layers. The multilayer structure with and without barrier layers is studied and a SXR reflectance of 24.3% at grazing incidence of 42° (near the Brewster angle) is measured at $\lambda=2.44$ nm.

The Cr/V multilayer is designed with a d-spacing of $d=1.8$ nm and a thickness ratio of $\gamma\sim 0.5$ (V layer thickness to the d-spacing). The multilayer will be working around the Brewster angle (45°) as a soft X-ray polarizer near the V-L absorption edge ($\lambda=2.42$ nm). All multilayers were fabricated by direct current magnetron sputtering technique. The base pressure in the deposition chamber is 2.0×10^{-4} Pa. High purity argon (99.999%) is used as the sputtering gas with a sputtering

pressure of 1 mTorr (0.13 Pa). The deposition rate of Cr, V, and B₄C is 0.05 nm/s, 0.02 nm/s and 0.01 nm/s, respectively. The multilayers were deposited on super-polished silicon wafers with a root-mean-squared (RMS) surface roughness of 0.2 nm.

Four multilayer samples with 30 bilayers were first deposited, with no B₄C barrier layer, with B₄C barrier layer at one of the interfaces (Cr-on-V or V-on-Cr), and with barrier layers at both interfaces, respectively, to study the effect of barrier layers. The barrier layer thickness was set as 0.1nm for the four samples and the Cr and V layer thickness were decreased equally in order to maintain the same d-spacing of 1.8 nm. The multilayers were measured by grazing incidence X-ray reflectometry (GIXR) at Cu-K α emission line ($\lambda=0.154$ nm) and fitted using the IMD software to determine the layer thickness and interface width [12]. In the fitting procedures, error function was selected as the interface profile function to describe the optical constants change across the interface [12]. Due to the small optical contrast between Cr and V at $\lambda=0.154$ nm, the 1st order peak reflectance of the multilayer is low in theory. Nevertheless, the multilayer without barrier layers displays the lowest reflectance of $R_{1st} = 2.6 \times 10^{-4}$ (figure 1 (a)). The fitted result gives large interface widths of $\sigma = 0.45\text{-}0.55$ nm. After introducing 0.1 nm B₄C barrier layer at a single interface (Cr-on-V or V-on-Cr), the Bragg peak reflectivity is significantly enhanced. As engineering the two different interfaces gives very similar results, only the Cr-on-V interface engineered sample is shown here (figure 1 (b)), with $R_{1st} = 5.6 \times 10^{-4}$ and interface widths of $\sigma = 0.27\text{-}0.35$ nm. For the sample with B₄C barrier layer at both interfaces (figure 1 (c)), the layer structure is further improved compared to the single interface engineered case, with the smallest interface widths of $\sigma = 0.21\text{-}0.31$ nm.

An optimization of the barrier layer thickness from 0.1 nm to 0.3 nm (introduced at both interfaces) was also performed, while the multilayer d-spacing was always kept as 1.8 nm. It is found that the multilayer with 0.1nm B₄C displays the best layer structure while the interface width actually increases a little with thicker barrier layer. For the multilayer with 0.3 nm B₄C, the fitted interface widths are $\sigma = 0.24\text{-}0.33$ nm (figure 1 (d)). This can be caused by the fact that further increasing the barrier layer thickness results in an even thinner Cr and V layer (in order to keep the same d-spacing), and probably a larger layer roughness at the early stage of layer growth [13].

Fig. 1 Grazing incidence X-ray reflectance measurement (at $\lambda = 0.154$ nm) and fitting results of 30 bilayers Cr/V multilayers, without B₄C barrier (a), with 0.1 nm B₄C at Cr-on-V interface (b), with 0.1 nm B₄C at both interfaces, with 0.3 nm B₄C at both interfaces.

To reach the maximum reflectance of Cr/V multilayer at around 45 degree, a bilayer number of more than 500 is needed. This will require a continuous deposition lasting for about 20 hours which demands a high accuracy and stability of the machine. For a first demonstration of the high reflectance multilayer, three samples with 100, 200, and 300 bilayers were deposited, all with 0.1nm B₄C barrier layer at both interfaces. The samples were measured by GIXR and atomic force microscope (AFM) to study the layer structure and surface morphology changes with number of bilayers. The GIXR results display an increasing reflectance of the 1st Bragg peak from 0.29% to 0.55% ($\lambda=0.154$ nm) for the samples with 100 bilayers to 200 bilayers, respectively. For the 300 bilayers sample, the reflectance is only increased to 0.63% while the Bragg peak is a little broadened as shown in figure 2. The GIXR curve of the 300 bilayers sample was fitted using the IMD software. Layer thickness drifts of Cr and V were added from the bottom to the top of the stack to account for the broadened peak. The instrumental beam divergence was also taken into account here. The fitted results display a small interface width of $\sigma = 0.21\text{-}0.31$ nm which is almost the same as the 30 bilayers sample. A d-spacing increase of 0.04 nm was found from the bottom to the top layers. The fitted structure will be further confirmed by the SXR reflectivity measurement later. It is indicated that the interface structure of the 300 bilayers sample is almost the same as the multilayer with 30 bilayers, while the limited enhancement of the 1st order reflectance from 200 to 300 bilayers is mainly caused by the deteriorated periodicity of the stack during the long-time deposition process [14,15].

Fig. 2 Grazing incidence X-ray reflectance measurement (at $\lambda = 0.154$ nm) and fitting result of 300 bilayers Cr/V multilayers, with 0.1 nm B₄C at both interfaces. The inset figure displays the measured and fitted results of the 1st order Bragg peak in linear scale.

The surface morphology of the [B₄C/Cr/B₄C/V] multilayers with different number of bilayers was measured by AFM. The images were taken over an area of $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$ with 256×256 points. The multilayer with 30 bilayers exhibits a RMS surface roughness of 0.18 nm. After increasing the number of bilayers to 100, 200, and 300, the RMS surface roughness is still maintained as 0.18-0.20 nm. The image of the 300 bilayers sample is shown in figure 3, with a peak-to-valley height difference of only 1.5 nm and a roughness of 0.19 nm. No roughness accumulation was observed with increasing number of bilayers, which is consistent with the result of GIXR measurement.

Fig. 3 AFM image of the [B₄C/Cr/B₄C/V] multilayer with 300 bilayers.

The internal structure and morphology of the multilayer samples without barrier layer ($N=30$) and with 0.1 nm barrier layer at both interfaces ($N=200$), were further characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The measurements were performed using the FEI Tecnai G2 F20 equipment in Materials Analysis Technology Inc. High resolution bright field images and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns are shown in figure 4. For the multilayer without B₄C barrier (figure 4 (a)), a layered structure can be partially seen in which the bright layers are V and the dark layers are Cr. Crystalline grains with different orientations are observed in the structure while most of the lattice planes are non-parallel to the layer boundaries. Some of the grains even grow across several layers. The SAED image (figure 4 (b)) displays a series of diffraction spots which are indexed as cubic structure of V (110), V (200), and V (220). It means that the vanadium layers in the Cr/V system are partially crystallized even when 0.9 nm thick. The non-parallel growth of the vanadium grains (with respect to the layer interfaces) can cause the large interface width of the multilayer, as indicated in the GIXR result (figure 1 (a)). For the multilayer with B₄C barriers at both interfaces (figure 4 (c)), a regular layered structure is clearly observed. Due to the very thin layers and the low mass contrast between Cr and V, the image quality is limited. Nevertheless, no grains or lattice planes were found in the bright field image. A series of images were taken from the bottom to the top of the 200-bilayers stack which exhibits very similar structures. The SAED image of the multilayer (figure 4 (d)) displays a broadened diffraction ring. It indicates that the layer structure is close to an amorphous state while the broadened ring can be caused by the weak diffraction from the fine grains with a few locally ordered atomic planes inside the layers. It is evident that the 0.1 nm B₄C layers significantly suppress the crystallization of the V layers, resulting in a smaller interface width as compared to the regular Cr/V multilayer. It is worth to note that, although we use the B₄C barrier layers in the discussion, the layer structure improvement is probably from the boron and carbon atoms and the related compound formation at the interfaces, rather than from the ultrathin layer itself [16]. Further explanation will need other characterizations that will be discussed elsewhere.

Fig. 4 TEM bright field images and SAED patterns of Cr/V multilayers without B₄C barrier (a) (b), and with barrier layers (c) (d), respectively.

The SXR reflectivity of the multilayer sample with 300 bilayers was measured at the Bending magnet for Emission Absorption and Reflectivity (BEAR) beamline at the ELETTRA synchrotron [17]. It was measured at grazing incidence angle of 45°, 43°, and 42° in order to study the spectral response at different wavelengths near the V-L edge. The incident light is first set as almost 100% s-polarized to measure the s-polarized reflectance. As shown in figure 5, the multilayer has a reflectance of 3.3% at 2.56 nm, under the incidence of 45°. By reducing the grazing incidence angle, the peak reflectance position is shifted to smaller wavelengths. In this case, a higher reflectance is generated due to the lower absorption of vanadium at the vicinity of the absorption edge. A peak reflectance of 10% is obtained at 2.48 nm (under the incidence of 43°), while a maximum reflectance of 24.3% is obtained at 2.44 nm (under the incidence of 42°). To the best knowledge of the authors, this is the highest s-polarized reflectance reported, working around the Brewster angle near the V-L edge in the water window region. The SXR reflectivity curves were further fitted which gives interface widths of $\sigma = 0.18$ nm-0.23 nm and a slight increase of the d-spacing of 0.035 nm from the bottom to the top of the stack. The thickness drift is almost the same as the one obtained in the GIXR results, while the interface width is a little smaller. The latter one can be attributed to the different ranges of spatial frequency of roughness that the soft X-ray or hard X-ray reflectance is sensitive to. The similar fitted results confirm that the fitted model is valid for the fabricated

multilayer structure. If the layer thickness drift can be corrected during the deposition, the peak reflectance will be further increased from 24.3% to 28.3%, according to the calculation. If a saturated number of bilayers of $N=500$ is used, another boost of 3% for the reflectance can be obtained. The p-polarized reflectance of the multilayer was also measured at 45° incidence, which is only 0.03% at $\lambda=2.56$ nm. The polarization degree ($(R_s - R_p)/(R_s + R_p)$) of the multilayer working at 45° is 98.2% that is high enough for polarization experiments.

Fig. 5 The s-polarized SXR reflectivity of [B₄C/Cr/B₄C/V] multilayer with 300 bilayers measured at grazing incidence of 42° , 43° , and 45° (circles). The theoretical fitted curves are also shown (solid lines).

In summary, high reflectance Cr/V multilayers with B₄C barrier layers are developed for the water window region. The multilayer interface widths are significantly reduced after the introduction of 0.1 nm B₄C layers which can be attributed to the suppression of crystallization of the vanadium layers. A maximum reflectance of 24.3% is obtained at $\lambda=2.441$ nm under the grazing incidence of 42° . The high reflectance mirror paves the way for polarimetry experiments in the wavelength region of $\lambda=2.42$ - 2.73 nm. For the normal incidence application that requires even smaller d-spacing, the B₄C barrier layers should also work. However, an accurate characterization of the extremely thin layer structure is needed and the improving effect of the barrier layers may be different.

Funding. National Natural Science Foundation of China (11505129, 11443007); Shanghai Pujiang Program (15PJ1408000); The National Key Scientific Instrument and Equipment Development Project (2012YQ13012505); The Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities.

Acknowledgment. The SXR reflectivity measurements were carried out at the ELETTRA synchrotron in the framework of Proposal No. 20145172.

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